

Modifying the Rules of Gravity – 8T

O Manor

June 23, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of the coupling constants series using the framework of Variational curvature, in particular using the new insight regarding bosons as net curvature on the Einstein manifold, one would like to suggestion for a modification of the rules of gravity and will provide a testable prediction to his suggested idea.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.13)$$

The modification: gravity would be proportional to the number of photons at a spatial cross section. The number of photons at a certain cross section is a function of the time that they travel from the source to the target, and so a function of the distance. The modification is suggested since in the 8T framework bosons were proven to be net curvature on the manifold, given by equation (1.13). To estimate the "gravitational effect" there must be an estimation of the photons, their number across the spatial section and in addition their wavelength. Gravitons are not mediating the long scale interactions among planets due to their spin two trait, and no graviton was even detected near the atmosphere. Here is the prediction.

If we could estimate how much photon rays are scattering each star in the solar system, there should be a relationship between that measured numbers to the intensity gravity at that point. A direct correlation. The more photons scattering a star, the stronger the "gravitational effect" and vice versa. An additional prediction can be made: Graviton will not be found propagating at long range, i.e. among stars, only at very short ranges, similar to the strong interaction. That is because it has spin two which vanish.

$$\left[2N^2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.14)$$

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow 2N(g) \quad (1.15)$$

So overall two predictions were made:

(1) Gravity is proportional to the number of photons scattered at area, assuming all similar wavelength at all distances.

(2) Gravity is mediated by net curvature propagating long range, i.e. spin one particles. Moreover, not spin two that is associated with a short range. The graviton is short ranged due to its spin two and will never be found crossing large matrix distances. It would be similar to the strong interaction.

Analysis were made according the spin classification of the 8T framework, given by the primordial coupling constants series in second representation:

Spin zero: (2N variations)

Matter with spin one-half: (2N variations + 3)

Bosons with spin one: (2N variations + 3) + N_v

Bosons with higher spin integers: (2N variations + 3) + N_{v1} + N_{v2} + ...

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)